

Wafer level manufacturing of photonic biosensors with integrated active components

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Introduction

Biosensors are valuable tools in a wide range of application areas such as medical diagnostics, agri-food, and environmental monitoring. Compared to other technologies, photonic biosensors offer advantageous features such as simultaneous detection of multiple biomarkers with a high analytical sensitivity on a small surface area. In addition, photonic chips are made by standard CMOS-compatible fabrication techniques, which ensures scalability and low cost per chip at high volume.

A promising possibility is the integration of light sources, detectors, or other active components on the photonic chip, resulting in a hybrid Photonic Integrated Circuit (PIC). This enables further miniaturization of biosensor systems, e.g., for development of handheld devices in Point-of-Care (PoC) applications.

Despite encouraging results, there are still several technological challenges to be solved to enable scalable manufacturing of hybrid biosensor PICs. The Horizon 2020 project PHOTO-SENS* addresses some of these challenges and builds on previous developments [1]. It uses a photonic chip based on silicon nitride (TriPLeX) waveguide technology [2], featuring integrated light source (VCSEL), detectors (photodiodes, PDs), and temperature sensor (NTC thermistor). Beside integration of these components, fabrication of a hybrid biosensor PIC also involves several chemical processes to modify and biofunctionalize the PIC surface for the selective and sensitive recognition and binding of biomarkers.

PICs are made on wafers by advanced cleanroom processes. A single wafer may contain hundreds or even thousands of PICs. From a manufacturing (cost) perspective, it is beneficial to separate the wafer into individual chips as late as possible. Therefore, one of the main challenges in PHOTO-SENS is to develop a consistent and scalable process flow starting from a wafer with bare chips, and resulting in functional hybrid biosensor PICs which can be further integrated with microfluidics and read-out electronics.

In this paper, the developments towards such a process flow are outlined. First, the design and fabrication of the PIC wafers is described, followed by the wafer level integration of the components. Then, wafers are material-selectively coated to enable local biofunctionalization of the sensing waveguides. Singulation of the coated hybrid PICs into individual chips is achieved using stealth dicing.

PIC design and fabrication

Each PHOTO-SENS PIC comprises 6 biosensor elements configured as an array of asymmetric Mach-Zehnder Interferometers (aMZIs) [3]. Each aMZI consists of two spiral-shaped waveguide arms, one of which responds to the presence of biomarkers, and the other one serving as a reference. Binding of a biomarker to the waveguide surface results in a local change of the refractive index, which is detected as a change of the output signal of the aMZI. The presence of 6 sensor elements on a chip enables parallel detection of multiple

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biomarkers and control measurements in a single sample. The PIC also comprises 2 calibration/reference channels.

Ultimately, the PIC will be placed in a microfluidic cartridge, enabling sample and buffer solutions to flow over the aMZIs. However, the integrated components of the hybrid PIC should not come in contact with any liquids. Figure 1 shows the design of the PHOTO-SENS PIC and the different functional areas. The overall dimensions of the PIC are 3.0 x 5.0 mm².

Figure 1 – Design of the PHOTO-SENS PIC, showing the different functional areas: A (blue, 6 aMZI sensors in microfluidic flow channel), B (green, hybrid integration of VCSEL, PD, and NTC), and C (yellow, contact area with microfluidic cartridge to form the microfluidic flow channel). Also visible in this area are alignment markers for spotting (see below).

The PICs were fabricated on 4" wafers by Lionix International (Enschede). Approximately 300 PHOTO-SENS PICs fit on a wafer. Waveguides are based on a stoichiometric Si₃N₄ core with a height of 100 nm and a width of 1000 nm. This core is on top of a 6 μm thermal SiO₂ substrate and covered by a 4 μm SiO₂ top cladding. At places where the aMZIs need to interact with the sample, the top cladding is etched away locally, exposing the Si₃N₄ waveguide to the sample or buffer solution.

Integration of components

Hybrid integration of active (III-V) and passive (silicon-based) photonic chips by edge coupling has been a proven technique for producing working photonic devices. However, it is unsuitable for integration on a wafer scale, where the chip edges are not exposed for making optical connections. Moreover, the electrical path between two adjacent chips is typically large (dominated by the wire bonds). Flip chip assembly, on the other hand, places the components on top of each other. This means that the integration interface is the top surface of the silicon chip, allowing the bonding process to be carried out on wafer scale. Compared to edge coupling, it enables the development of high density and low footprint hybrid PICs. Despite the added complexity, flip chip assembly can be very cost effective at higher production volumes.

The PHOTO-SENS wafer comprises Si₃N₄ waveguide circuitry with a grating coupler for optical inputs and outputs and electrical bond pads for electrical integration of other photonic components. These optical and electrical interfaces are located in area B as shown in Figure 1. To produce a complete PHOTO-SENS hybrid PIC, a single mode 850 nm VCSEL and two 1x4 arrays of gallium arsenide (GaAs) PIN PDs are integrated by flip chip bonding. The gold finished metallization of the VCSEL makes a suitable flip chip bond with the gold finished metallization of the chip. The PDs are top-side illuminated and operate at 850 nm wavelength with a

signal-ground (SG) pad configuration and they are solder bumped with gold-tin (AuSn). To monitor and regulate the temperature of the hybrid PIC, a NTC thermistor is directly mounted onto the chip.

The flip chip process is a straightforward way of directly integrating top emitting optical sources (such as VCSELs) and top illuminated PDs onto a substrate, since the electrical connections and the optically active areas are both on the top surface of the chip. The uppermost layer of electrical interconnects terminates on metal pads. Flip chip technology relies on Au-Au thermal compression bonding for VCSEL integration and AuSn ball reflow for the integration of the PD arrays. The chips are flipped over so the bond pads and the optical windows are aligned with corresponding contact pads and grating couplers on the wafer. The method for making the connection then depends on the component being bonded. PD arrays are secured by fluxless solder reflow, VCSELs by thermocompression bonding, and NTC thermistors by electrically conductive adhesive.

Bonding of optoelectronic components requires submicron alignment precision. This is achieved using a Fineplacer Femto 2 automated flip chip bonding machine (Finetech, Berlin), on which the assembly process for the different components has been optimized. The rings around the optical windows of the components as well as the bond pad features are used as alignment fiducial structures between the III-V dies and the substrate.

The automated pick-and-place machine is equipped with two different solder ball (pad) reflow methods: conductive heating and laser assisted heating. In the case of conductive heating, heat is applied to both the substrate holder and tool head. This technique is not suitable for wafer level bonding, because the whole wafer would need to be reheated every time a PD array is placed. Therefore, laser assisted heating was adopted, where a laser beam is applied to the back of the substrate to locally reflow specific solder bumps within a limited area. This allows successive PD arrays to be transferred onto the wafer without compromising the bonds that have already been made. The III-V components are picked up and transferred to the wafer as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Wafer level flip-chip bonding of PDs. III-V dies (left) are individually transferred from a carrier and bonded to a wafer (right).

For the PHOTO-SENS PIC, four components (one VCSEL, two PD arrays, and one NTC) are populated onto every die on the wafer, see Figure 3. The assembly sequence of these components is dictated by the required temperatures to bond them to the substrate. The VCSELs are populated first via thermocompression bonding at 330 °C, followed by the PD arrays with solder reflow at 300 °C. Finally, the NTC thermistors are bonded using electrically conductive adhesive and post baked at 150 °C. Leveraging the advanced pick-and-place tool that uses machine vision to maintain precise alignment, a photonic component can be placed and bonded within 30 seconds with a precision better than 300 nm. This means that 120 photonic components can be

populated onto a silicon wafer in one hour, corresponding to the assembly of 30 complete hybrid PHOTOSENS PICs.

Figure 3 – III-V photonic components (VCSELs and PD arrays) and NTCs populated on a wafer.

Coating and biofunctionalization

To detect the biomarker of interest, bioreceptors need to be immobilized on the surface of the waveguide (biofunctionalization). The bioreceptors must be chosen such that they sensitively and specifically recognize and capture the biomarker. Only biomarkers that bind to the surface of the waveguide will be detected, and therefore only the exposed Si_3N_4 needs to be biofunctionalized. The surrounding SiO_2 , on the other hand, needs to be treated to prevent non-specific adsorption of biomolecules (biofouling).

Surfix has developed a nanocoating technology which enables the material-selective surface modification and biofunctionalization of Si_3N_4 vs. SiO_2 (Figure 4a). First, a carboxylic acid terminated coating is deposited on the Si_3N_4 surface of the waveguide, while the surrounding SiO_2 surface remains uncoated. In a second step, the SiO_2 surface is modified with an anti-biofouling layer such as poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG). Finally, bioreceptors are immobilized on the waveguide, e.g., by direct reaction with the carboxylic acid groups on the surface or other (physico)chemical methods.

The effectiveness of the material-selective biofunctionalization was demonstrated by immobilizing a fluorescently labelled protein on the waveguide. A fluorescence micrograph of the aMZI spiral (Figure 4b) clearly shows that the labelled proteins are only present on the waveguide. This result indicates that the material-selective coating enables biofunctionalization of the waveguide while preventing non-specific adsorption of bioreceptors on the surrounding area, thus enhancing the performance of the biosensor PIC.

Since there are 6 aMZIs on every PIC which may all require different bioreceptors, the sensor elements need to be individually addressable. This is achieved by a precision dispensing technique called spotting, which allows the deposition of picolitre droplets on a surface with a very high lateral precision and accuracy. For this, a sciFlexarrayer S3 (Scienion, Berlin) was used. To ensure correct spotting of bioreceptors on the different waveguides, alignment markers are present on each chip (see Figure 1).

Figure 4 – a) Schematic representation of a material-selectively coated and biofunctionalized aMZI spiral, showing immobilized bioreceptors (for example antibodies, indicated by the yellow molecules) on the carboxylic acid terminated coating (light blue) on the Si_3N_4 waveguide, and the anti-biofouling coating (dark blue) on the surrounding SiO_2 ; b) Fluorescence micrograph of a material-selectively coated aMZI spiral which has been biofunctionalized by immobilization of a fluorescently labelled protein.

For spotting, the bioreceptor is dissolved in a buffer solution with a composition that needs to be optimized for the stability and functionality of the bioreceptor, and its reactivity with the surface. To improve the wetting of the surface and to prevent premature evaporation, additives such as sugars or surfactants are added to adjust the viscosity and surface tension of the spotting buffer. Before spotting the bioreceptor solution on the individual sensor elements, the carboxylic acid groups on the waveguide surface are activated to enhance their reactivity towards the bioreceptor. The PEG coating prevents unwanted immobilization of bioreceptors on SiO_2 . Thus, the final result of the process is a PIC with 6 individually spotted, material-selectively biofunctionalized aMZIs.

Figure 5 – a) Wafer holder for material-selective nanocoating of up to 7 PIC wafers; b) Part of a material-selectively coated test wafer with large Si_3N_4 and SiO_2 areas (see magnification). Water droplets are deposited on the wafer for coating characterization by measurement of the water contact angle.

Die singulation by stealth dicing

Die singulation or wafer dicing is the process of separating the wafer into individual chips or dies for further assembly and packaging. In PHOTO-SENS, the wafer needs to be separated into individual hybrid PICs for further integration in the microfluidic cartridge. The presence of integrated components and organic coatings or even biomolecules on the wafer presents a challenge for the dicing process. Commonly used dicing techniques such as saw (blade) dicing and ablative laser dicing are not suitable for singulation of hybrid PIC biosensor chips, because of excessive heat development, use of cooling water, or formation of debris.

Therefore, we investigated singulation by stealth dicing, an advanced laser dicing technology which is dry and debris-free. [4] The stealth dicing process consists of three steps as shown in Figure 6. First, the wafer is fixed on a dicing tape which is mounted on a dicing ring. Then, a focused laser beam creates subsurface defects in the wafer along the lines where the dies need to be separated, leaving the front and back surfaces intact. Finally, dies are separated under radial tensile stress by tape expansion and can be picked from the foil for further assembly and packaging.

Figure 6 – a) Schematic representation of the stealth dicing (SD) process; b) stealth diced wafer before tape expansion; c) stealth diced wafer after tape expansion. Source: www.disco.co.jp.

Stealth dicing was performed by DISCO Hi-TEC Europe (Munich) on coated test wafers with Si_3N_4 and SiO_2 areas (the same wafer design that were previously used for development of the material-selective coating process), see Figure 7. It was demonstrated that the properties of the coatings on stealth diced chips were identical to those obtained for PICs that were coated after dicing. Thus, stealth dicing can be used to singulate coated PIC wafers without damaging the coatings and is therefore the singulation method of choice for the scalable manufacturing of (hybrid) PIC biosensors.

Figure 7 – Stealth diced wafer after tape expansion (3 dies have been removed).

Conclusion and outlook

In PHOTO-SENS, novel processes for the wafer scale production of hybrid biosensor PICs have been developed and verified. VCSELs, PDs, and NTC thermistors are flip chip bonded onto wafers with photonic circuitry by thermocompression bonding, laser assisted soldering, and adhesive bonding. Processes for wafer level material-selective coating and local biofunctionalization of populated wafers have been demonstrated. Finally, a stealth dicing process has been developed which is compatible with the presence of integrated components and coatings on the wafer. The next step is further integration of the hybrid biosensor PIC in a microfluidic cartridge, which will also be addressed in PHOTO-SENS.

References

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Abbreviations

aMZI	Asymmetric Mach-Zehnder Interferometer
CMOS	Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor
IVD	In Vitro Diagnostics
NTC	Negative Temperature Coefficient
PD	Photodiode
PEG	Poly(ethylene glycol)
PIC	Photonic Integrated Circuit
PoC	Point-of-Care
VCSEL	Vertical Cavity Surface Emitting Laser